

ROBS4CROPS

D 1.8 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (3)

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16920435

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016807

D1.7 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (3)

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Contributor(s)	Inputs were provided by each partner of the whole R4C Consortium. Most inputs come from the Large Scales Pilots' Leaders.
Work Package	WP1
Delivery Date (DoA)	31 Dec 2023
Actual Delivery Date	28 Dec 2023
Abstract:	<p>This document presents the perception of robotic systems for weeding application by farmers, on technical aspects. 1 Co-design session was held in 1 of the 4 Large-scale pilots, from which the data presented in this document has been extracted. It contains a description of how the discussions were held, what subjects on the different robotic solutions have been covered and the conclusions associated to them, and ways of improvements that will allow the project and external stakeholders to improve said robotic solutions. This deliverable D1.8 will mainly be used by partners in WP1 in this project, roboticists and external stakeholders, to know what needs to be improved on the robotic solutions that are experimented with in this project, in order to fit the farmer's needs and reach field maturity (TRL7).</p>

Document Revision History			
Date	Version	Author/Contributor/ Reviewer	Summary of main changes
23.12.28	1.0	Bertrand Pinel, Luc Dejonghe (TER)	Initial version

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	YES
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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ROBS4CROPS Consortium			
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4	SERRATER SL	SER	ES
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Funding Scheme: Innovation Action (IA) • Topic: H2020-ICT-46-2020

Start date of project: 01 January, 2021 • Duration: 48 months

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
CoDS	Co-Design Session
EU	European Union
EUT	Eurecat
FR	France
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIR	Giropoma
GR	Greece
LSP	Large Scale Pilot
NL	Netherlands
PDL	Permissioned Distributed Ledger
R4C	Robots4Crops
RaaS	Robot as a Service
ROI	Return On Investment
SER	Serrater
SP	Spain
TER	Terrena
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

For an introduction to the project and the large-scale pilots, see the introduction to D1.1 deliverable.

The purpose of this document is to get and detail the user's feedback after their experience with different robotic solutions. The objective is then to provide a wide variety of stakeholders, and especially the roboticists, with crucial information that will allow them to identify and chose areas for improvements that meet the final users' needs. This document complements the first deliverable "D1.1 - Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems".

In each year of the project, co-design sessions have been held in each of the large-scale pilots. The focus of these sessions was different in each year. In 2021, the farmers' technical needs and requirements have been collected in every LSP. In 2022, the main focus was on non-technical issues, like regulations or fundings. In 2023, the target was on getting the user's experience and opinion on the different robotic solutions, to fine-tune their requirements for the final product.

This document is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the structure and the methods of each LSP co-design session : what subjects they covered, who attended each session, how and when it was organized. Data collected during the CoDSs is described in sections 3, depending on the robotic solutions that have been discussed, the subsystem of the said robotic solution, and the nature of the data (Feedback or Questions). Finally, an analysis of the main improvements that we should address in the future will be presented in section 4 before taking a step back to check how we progressed on the technical matters that were raised during the first 3 years of this project.

Please note that LSP2 (Greece) and LSP3 (Spain) could not organise their 2023 session as planned, due to the limited timeframe available after the field operations. Consequently, section 3 of this deliverable only includes results of LSP1 (France).

Also, the results and details of the LSP4 (Netherlands) session held in 2023 have been included within an update of the deliverable "D1.7 - Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (2)" (instead of in the current document) because the 2023 LSP4 session addressed the same topics that were addressed in D1.7 .

2 Structure & Methods of each Co-Design Session

2.1. Topics

The topics addressed in the co-design sessions in 2023 included technical issues (such as specification of requirements) as well as non-technical issues (such as regulations and economics).

LSP1 (FR) : Technical matters – User’s experience

What did the winegrowers think of :

- The CEOL robot itself, and the new RX-20-H that Pellenc is about to commercialize
- The Manual remote control of the robot
- The mobile App “Automate”
- The mission generation web platform “PAM”

And how can it be improved ?

LSP2 (GR) : Technical matters – User’s experience

The co-design session for LSP2 was scheduled for November 2023. But it was decided to re-schedule the session for early 2023, due to the limited timeframe available after the field operations.

LSP3 (SP) : Technical matters – User’s experience

The co-design session for LSP3 was scheduled for November 2023. But it was decided to re-schedule the session for early 2023, due to the limited timeframe available after the field operations.

2.2. Type of stakeholders and participants

LSP 1 (FR) :

Table 1 - Type of stakeholder, Organisation and name of the participants of the 2023 LSP1 CoDS

Stakeholders	Organisation	Attendees
Organizer	Terrena (TER)	Ludovic PATTE
		Luc DEJONGHE
Producers	Winegrowers	7 Winegrowers
Institutes	IFV	Esteban F.
Advisors	LVVD	Stéphane P.
Distributors		Arthur A.
Roboticists	AgreenCulture (AGC)	Guillaume GREUSARD
		Hélène M.
		François B.
		Solenn A.
		Nicolas P.

2.3. Structure and organisation

LSP1 (FR):

Date	27/10/2023 + 06/11/2023
Duration	2 hours each
Structure	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Opening and stakeholders introduction2. The Robot3. The Manual remote4. The AGC smartphone app and the autonomous mode5. The mission generation web platform6. Conclusion <p>For part 2 to 5, the session was organized as follows :</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">I. Tests & material presentationII. Results presentationIII. Discussions over questions raised up during the users' experience tests conducted with the participating farmers in June & July 2023

LSP 1

Figure 1 - Pictures of some LSP 2023 CoDS

3 Results

All following information is categorised depending on its type :

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

3.1. The robotic solution

3.1.1. The CEOL robot

3.1.1.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Overall

- The compact and light architecture of the robot is its biggest feature.

The level of trust the farmers put in the robot

- In the first years, farmers want to work beside the robot on field tasks (such as pruning), IT or administrative tasks, to be able to monitor it. They don't fully trust it.

The CEOL work capacity

- The current CEOL robot would not be able to handle both inter-row and inter-vine work at the same time on heavy-soil or steep plots.
 - But this issue is not a big deal for farmers, as the main work the robot needs to accomplish is in the inter-vine.

- Farmers are curious to see the robot working on difficult soils.

The current CEOL robot is very climate-dependant : in dry conditions, it will have a harder time working compared to a tractor. On the other hand, it can get back to the plot more quickly in humid conditions, due to its lighter impact on the ground.

- This issue should be improved with the Pellenc robot, as it will use a more powerful engine.

The after-sale

- The winegrowers feel the need for support and after-sales service for the robot.
 - LVVD (Terrena's subsidiary) intends to put it in place.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

- Farmers asked about the dimensions of the CEOL robot and those of its successor, the RX-20-H from Pellenc.
 - The width comes into 3 options, identical for the 2 robots

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Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.1.1.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Overall, the vision of the final product

- Above all, farmers want a reliable and simple robot. Then the best would be to have access to modules and accessories to improve the robot, and make it fit the farmer's needs.
- Farmers would like the robot to have a high degree of autonomy, with a robot that detects issues and tries to solve them by itself when possible (examples : double-checking bumper alerts ; reversing the robot to remove obstructions such as clods and crop residue from the implements).

Energy autonomy

- For a diesel engine robot, 12h minimum. Plus, such a machine only needs to be refilled to be able to work 24h/24.
 - It is already the case, as the CEOL has an average autonomy >17h
- For an electric robot, farmers have a hard time finding the best solution.
 - With interchangeable batteries, a minimum of 4h of working time per battery. Which means farmers would need with 2 batteries minimum (depending on the charging time of the batteries).
 - For a consolidated vineyard, the ideal would be to have 1 or 2 batteries for a full workday (or a local charging station).
 - For a dispersed vineyard, the ideal would be to work with multiple smaller batteries, changed for fresh ones each time it is moved between plots.
 - For a vineyard cut in isolated blocks, the best would be to have local charging stations.

A possible evolution in a fully electric robot

- Overall, a full electric robot would be a great advantage for some farmers.
- For most farmers, the main interest of a fully electric robot is to reduce their carbon footprint.
The noise reduction is a secondary interest.
- But charging an electric robot can be difficult for some farmers : it depends on their farm's structure, the distance between their plots, etc.
Some farmers are not sure that an easy solution is feasible : it is illegal for a robot to drive on public roads, often preventing the robot from driving to a charging station by itself.
 - It is something on which the recent "Grand Défi de la Robotique Agricole", a project supported by the French government, is going to work.

Work quality

- Some farmers have experienced issues with the light weight of the tools the current CEOL robot can carry, which reduces the quality of the weeding.
 - The new Pellenc RX-20-H robot should be able to carry heavier tools and should thus answer this issue.

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- Farmers expressed the need to have a robot equipped with an implement capable of adjusting the height of its tools automatically, as it would increase the weeding quality by a lot on tilted plots, or plots which have an uneven ground.
 - This is not part of the 2024 Robs4Crops project experiments on LSP1 anymore.
- Some tools need high speeds (8 – 9km/h) to work properly, but the robot can legally only work at 6 km/h maximum.
 - This issue reduces the flexibility and usability of the robot compared to a tractor.
- The robot needs to be able to plough the inter-vines to be defined as “field-ready” (= TRL7), which has not been fully demonstrated yet, especially on narrow vines. In addition, farmers stated that if the robot can plough, it can carry out any weeding task.

Work monitoring

- Having visual feedback on the robot’s work is essential for farmers.
 - The new Pellenc robot is equipped with 4 cameras for a 360° vision, and thus meets this need.
- Some farmers prefer cameras to be low (lower than those of the Pellenc robot), to be able to have a good view of the tools and adjust their height.
 - But that raises an issue, as the cameras could get dirty quickly, thus making them useless.

Other farmers prefer to have a global view of the surroundings and the robot (which the Pellenc robot offers). But would still like to see a camera added behind the tools, at the implement’s height.

- On the implement of the robot, farmers are interested by having “smart” implements, equipped with sensors that can detect blocking of the implements or other type of equipment. But they made it clear that the tools had to remain reliable and durable as much as possible, and that they had to remain tractor compatible.

Security

- All security measures that could be improved on the CEOL robot are already added to the Pellenc version. Thus farmers don’t need new additions. The main issue remains the impossibility to navigate on communal paths, which board a lot of vineyards. This means that either the regulations need to be changed, or farmers need to reduce the crops’ surfaces to let some space for the robot to navigate their fields.
 - It is something on which the recent “Grand Défi de la Robotique Agricole”, a project supported by the French government, is going to work.
- As a bonus, it would benefit the farmers to have an intercom directly on the robot, to be able quickly talk to people around the robot, to help field colleagues, or to scare off potential troublemakers.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

- What protocol would the robot follow if it encounters a problem overnight ?
 - According to technical experts, the best way to deal with it would be : If the robot faces an issue overnight, it shuts down and pause the ongoing operation for the rest of night (a period defined by the farmer). That way, the farmer doesn’t have to be troubled when he doesn’t want to.

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Security

- Is the robot allowed to run without anybody next to it ?
 - In the fields only.
- Is the robot allowed to drive on communal paths and public roads ?
 - No.

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

- What happens if it rains during an operation, making it difficult ? The robot would need to stop.
 - Maybe adding humidity sensors on the robot would allow it to detect the rain by itself, so it can pause the ongoing operation and resume it later ?
 - Or by linking the robot's computer to the nearest weather station ?

3.2. The components of the robotic solution

3.2.1. CEOL – Manual remote

3.2.1.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Ergonomics

- The ergonomics of the manual remote control are important to gain precision and efficiency, especially when weeding with the robot manually. The ergonomics of the CEOL's remote could be improved.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.1.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Ergonomics

- An optimal manual remote should look like a drone remote : Small, light, and compact. With the basic controls as analogue buttons, switches and joysticks, but linkable with a smartphone (See picture below).
That way, all the controls are grouped on one platform, with the sturdy navigation controls on the analogue remote, and all the more advanced controls on the digital App of the Smartphone.

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Figure 2 - Drone remote controller, discussed during LSP1 co-design session

- The hitch position button of the CEOL's remote controller is not precise enough, it would be better to have an analogue thumbwheel (like the one on the drone controller, see picture below).

Figure 3 - Analogue thumbwheel of a drone remote controller, discussed during LSP1 co-design session

- To answer the question « Can joysticks be replaced by digital controls on a smartphone ? » : no, analogue controller can't be replaced by a fully digital controller, as it needs to be durable enough to withstand any weather : rain, high humidity, low temperatures, mud, etc. It also has to work properly when the user is using gloves.

Range of the remote

- For manual navigation with the analogue controller, a range of 50 – 100 m would be necessary.
- For adjusting the weeding parameters, an unlimited range (using 4G) would be necessary : for some farmers, the ideal solution would be to be able to drive the robot on great distances, to unblock it when it encounters an obstacle that is avoidable by a human pilot.
 - This aspect has not yet been defined properly within the regulations.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.2. CEOL – Digital app

3.2.2.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- The app is doing its job, but it lacks some information that are needed by farmers to work properly, and some essential functionalities.
See part 3.2.2.2. for details on possible improvements.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.2.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Displayed information

- It would be very useful to have an easy access to a dashboard similar to the one of a tractor, with the fuel level (or battery charge status), engine temperature, etc.
 - It is important to be able to monitor those parameters regularly.
 - This is a feature that AGC is planning on including in the new version of the App
- It would also be useful to have access to an estimation of the time remaining on an operation, rather than a percentage progress. This would allow them to optimize the time they have to do other tasks in parallel.
- It would be optimal to have multiple levels of use of the App (like the Amazone terminal "AmaTron 4") :
 - Basic mode with base function
 - Intermediate mode,
 - Advanced mode with access to all parameters (including those affecting the integrity of the machine).
- On a side note, it would also be useful to have access to some "Agrointelligence" data, with sensors on the robot that would detect diseases on the crops, growth zones, missing vine stocks, etc.

Farmer's work organisation & efficiency

- It would be essential to keep all the missions' progress saved. It is important to be able to switch from one mission to another without cancelling the previous one. Particularly for the case of managing several parallel missions that have been interrupted by bad conditions (e.g. rain).
= A farmer needs to be able to keep the progress of a mission until he presses the "Done" button.
- It would be very important to be able to choose the driving orientation (or navigation direction) before launching the mission, as it increases the weeding quality of the inter-vine work.

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Data provision

- It would also be very useful to record all the data acquired during the operations, to allow farmers to make statistical analyses of the work done in the vineyard, to make some comparison between cultivation methods, tools, machines, etc.

Encountering and communicating an error

- If the robot encounters an issue during a mission, farmers need it to notify them quickly : No need for complex information, the optimal solution would be an SMS (that doesn't require a 3G/4G connection) with a quick message setting out the nature of the error = "Tool jammed", or "Obstacle encountered", or "Engine failure" (or redirecting to the app where the error should be explained). With the option of watching the situation with the cameras, then restarting or not restarting the robot if necessary.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.3. CEOL – Mission generator

3.2.3.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- The web platform is doing its job, but it lacks some useful functionalities. See part 3.2.3.2. for details on possible improvements.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.3.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- The winegrowers would like to be able to set default "pre-recorded" work parameters when generating a mission for the robot. That way, they would be able to quicken the start of each operation, as they would only have to fine-tune each parameter on the field if needed.
- Among those parameters, the working height should be set automatically according to the type of tool used during the mission, and the space it takes.
- It would also be useful to get an estimation of the amount of time the mission will take when generating it, to help farmers organize their work schedule.

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Questions raised by farmers, and answered

[// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

[// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

4 Conclusion & Final analysis

4.1. Main lessons from this year

On the CEOL :

Overall, the architecture of the CEOL robot is good and addresses the users' requirements that were set in 2021. But it still needs to be improved to reach field maturity (TRL7).

- Farmers don't fully trust autonomous robots yet, as the technology is new.
 - The CEOL robot (or the newer version) has yet to prove itself in difficult soils.
 - Farmers still feel the need to be supported with using the robot, at least until they get familiar with that technology.
 - Farmers want a reliable and simple robot (with modules available to upgrade it), and that is capable of handling simple situations autonomously (weeding operations and avoidable obstacles).
 - Farmers are very interested in a fully electric robot (for environmental purposes), but they question its energy autonomy and the current solutions associated with it.
 - Farmers want to access more information during the field operations : visual contact with the direct environment of the robot, and visual contact over the implements.
- ➔ *A lot of the farmers' feedback will be addressed with the new version of the CEOL : the Pellenc RX-20.*

The manual remote control of the CEOL does the job, but its ergonomics could be improved.

- Farmers need something like that of a drone : Small, light, and compact. With the basic controls as analogue buttons, switches and joysticks, but linkable with a smartphone.

The digital app of the CEOL robot does the job, but could be improved with the addition of some essential functionalities to reach a mature state.

- Have access to more information about the robot's systems (battery charge level, fuel level, etc.)
 - Have access to more information about the on-going mission (mission time remaining)
 - Keep all the missions' progress saved until they are finished (crucial to reach field maturity), and recording them afterwards.
- ➔ *A lot of the farmers' feedback will be addressed with the new version of the app, developed by AGreenCulture.*

The mission generation platform of the CEOL robot does the job, but misses some useful functionalities.

- Setting pre-recorded parameters for every field operations.
- Estimate the time a generated mission will take.

4.2. What progress compared to 2021

On the CEOL :

Compared to 2021, the CEOL robot has reached a higher degree of maturity : it is capable of achieving a complete weeding season, but not yet by itself as it still needs to be monitored closely.

Overall, farmers are happy of what the CEOL have become and what is it capable of, but

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they still need the robot to become more reliable and autonomous in order to find it “field ready”.

4.3. What still needs to be addressed to reach field maturity

Overall, on the CEOL :

- The robot reliability and autonomy
(should be partially addressed by the newer version, the Pellenc RX-20)
- The ergonomics of its manual remote controller
- The information displayed in the Digital App (Mobile app and Misison generation app), and its functionalities, to give the farmer more control over the robot and their work organisation
(should be partially addressed by the newer version of the App)

Additionally, a specific question has not yet been answered during the LSP1 co-design session :

- **What happens if it rains during an operation, making it difficult ?** The robot would need to stop.
Some solutions have been discussed, like the integration of humidity sensors on the robot or a link with a weather station.
- ➔ This issue could potentially be addressed by the Robs4Crops project, with the Farming Controller.

4.4. How to improve our methods

In France, the weather forced the co-design session to be postponed, originally set in July after the field test sessions with the farmers. As a result, the session was partially held remotely, and the questions were not as fresh in everybody’s mind.

Even tough the session went well, improving the communication between farmers and organizers could benefit the overall organization, and prevent people to get frustrated by multiple postponing.

Annex 1 – Reference questions to ask during the French 2023 CoDS, based on the users' experience tests organized beforehand

1. The robot
 - What are your needs in terms of robot autonomy (battery/thermal) ?
 - Would a 100% electric robot be a huge advantage ?
 - What level of equipment robustness do you need (track units in particular) ?
 - Would an additional security tool such as a videophone be useful ?
 - Are there any other safety features that you feel could be improved or added ?
 - After 2 years of operation, how could the robot's work be further improved ?

2. The manual remote
 - How can the ergonomics of the radio control be improved ? (size and shape of buttons, shape of the remote).
 - What size and weight should the remote be for your application ?
 - What range should the radio control have for your use ?

3. The AGC smartphone app and the autonomous mode
 - How can you benefit from visual feedback from a camera ?
 - Would having access to the remaining fuel level help you in your organisation ?
 - Would it be useful to know how much time is left on an ongoing mission ?
 - Would it be important to be able to keep track of the progress of an unfinished mission ?
 - Would a history of the tasks carried out with the robot be useful ?
 - What information would you like to have when the robot encounters a problem ?
 - Would it be interesting to be able to choose which way the mission is read before launching it ?
 - Would you like access to more specific information ? (example : engine temperature, engine speed, etc.)

4. The mission generation platform
 - Would it be useful to have a parameter that automatically switches the direction of the mission at each launch ?
 - Would you like to be able to choose the speed of the robot when it is outside the row ?
 - Would it be useful for you to know how long a mission takes before it is generated, when you set the parameters ?
 - Would you like to be able to adjust the hitch position at the beginning and end of the rows ?

5. Conclusion
 - Of all the elements discussed, which would you highlight the most ?
 - What are your favourite features of the CEOL robot so far ?
 - What do you expect from LVVD as a future distributor of the robot ?